

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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LINGUOCULTURAL ANALYSIS OF RUSSIAN HUMOR

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Abstract. *Humor, as a linguistic and cultural phenomenon, is a unique form of verbal communication. Russian humor is an essential part of the global cultural landscape, representing a repetition of commonly accepted norms within a national culture. It reflects the cultural perceptions of the Russian people and their attitude toward life. This article explores the definition of humor, compares humor with related concepts such as “anecdote” and “irony,” analyzes humor in a cultural context, examines its functions, and attempts to linguoculturally analyze the cultural connotations embedded in Russian humor. Additionally, the study investigates the role of Russian humor in verbal communication and highlights Russian cultural concepts and attitudes toward life reflected in humor.*

Keywords: *Russian humor, language, cultural background.*

Introduction. In the Russian language, the word “humor” is a transliteration of the Latin word humor, which originally meant bodily fluid. The ancient Greek physician Hippocrates believed that bodily fluids contained blood, phlegm, yellow bile, and black bile, and that their varying proportions determined different temperaments (Xu, 1990: 2-3). Over time, the meaning of the term gradually evolved into its modern-day literary, artistic, and aesthetic interpretations. Although humor is a common phenomenon in everyday life, defining it remains a complex task. In the 17th century, the renowned British playwright William Congreve stated: “Defining humor is an endless task—there are as many definitions as there are people” (Chen Xuyin, 1989: 70). This article presents several definitions from academic sources:

- “Humor consists of verbal and non-verbal behavior and is the ability to understand, appreciate, and create humor.” — Oxford English Dictionary
- “The best definition of humor is perhaps the simplest: Humor is everything that is funny.” — New Era Encyclopedia (USA)
- “Humor is something interesting, funny, and meaningful.” — Modern Chinese Dictionary
- “Humor is a form of artistic technique. It is characterized by an easygoing and meaningful laughter while simultaneously prompting people to deeply reflect on the subject of the joke.” — Dictionary (1989: 891)

Based on these interpretations from different regions and cultural backgrounds, this article summarizes humor as follows:

1. An innate quality of openness and optimism in human nature.

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2. The ability to perceive and express the humorous aspects of life.
3. Speech or behavior that evokes laughter.
4. Witty and subtle expressions that encourage thoughtful reflection.

Humor is a unique phenomenon in the Russian language and culture, distinct from other terms that convey meanings of fun and amusement. To better understand the differences among humor, anecdote, and satire, this section compares these three concepts.

Humor and Anecdote. As previously analyzed, humor is an organic combination of taste and philosophy. It induces laughter while prompting an understanding of the underlying meaning or philosophical subtext. The main characteristics of humor are wit and laughter, which form its foundation. Humor encompasses a broad spectrum of comedic phenomena and can transform objectively non-humorous situations into amusing ones (Livengart A.Ya., 1986: 45).

The term anecdote originates from the Greek word *anekdoton*, meaning “unpublished” or “previously unknown.” In the Russian language, *Literary Encyclopedic Dictionary* defines it as follows:

1. In the mid-18th century, a short narrative literary genre with humorous elements became popular in Russia. By the mid-19th century, the term also referred to a genre of folk literature, characterized by wit and humor, often with unexpected endings. From this, it is evident that anecdotes are a form of oral folklore that reflect contemporary events and serve as a unique linguistic form of humor. Based on the above analysis, we can summarize the unique characteristics of humor as follows:

1. Humor has various mediums—it can be expressed not only through language but also through performance, images, sculpture, etc.
2. Humor also refers to an ability—either the ability to create jokes or the ability to perceive them, also known as a sense of humor.

Cultural Analysis of Russian Humorous Discourse. Language is a carrier of culture and an objective reflection of it. Humor, as an artistic means that unites taste and philosophy, is a linguistic expression of human intellect and an important tool for communication. Through humor, we can observe a people’s environment, way of life, social relationships, personal characteristics, and psychological traits.

In Russian culture, humor holds a special and irreplaceable place. This section attempts to interpret the connotations of Russian culture through humor in everyday life, including in politics, work, and family. It also aims to explore Russian values, moral concepts, and behavioral norms.

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Cultural Analysis of Political Humor. Russian humor covers a wide range of topics, one of the most prominent being political humor, which focuses on political events and figures while critiquing negative aspects of political life. Political humor presents different perspectives on political reality, allowing people to understand the political climate of a country, assess its political and cultural life, and recognize connections between historical and contemporary political phenomena. For example:

- “How will we live without Khrushchev?”

“The same way—in Khrushchyovkas.”

The term Khrushchyovka refers to simple, mass-produced buildings constructed during Khrushchev’s rule, combining Khrushchev and trushchoba (slum). This joke highlights the poor living conditions of Soviet citizens during Khrushchev’s leadership. Additionally, the phrase *po-brezhnevu* (same way, under Brezhnev) plays on Brezhnev’s name and *po-prezhnemu* (the same as before), mocking Brezhnev’s incompetence and the stagnation of Soviet society under his rule. Here, humor is used to reference historical facts while subtly satirizing both leaders.

- “Who is your father?”

“Comrade Stalin!”

“And who is your mother?”

“The Soviet Motherland!”

“And what do you want to be?”

“An orphan!”

This joke reveals the deep dissatisfaction of Soviet citizens under Stalin’s rule. The child in the joke would rather be an orphan than have Stalin and the Soviet state as parents, reflecting the people’s suffering and despair under his leadership. The humor in this anecdote captures the immense hardship of Soviet life, portraying the people’s desire to break free from Stalin’s oppressive rule.

These examples illustrate how political humor served as both a critique of and an escape from the harsh realities of Soviet life, offering a glimpse into the cultural and historical consciousness of the Russian people. Many humorous works are built on skepticism and criticism of society. They reflect various negative aspects of social life and the daily experiences of Russian people. However, the social conditions of different ethnic groups vary. To fully understand this type of humor, one must be aware of the specific social characteristics of the nation to avoid misinterpretation. Russian humor highlights a wide range of social issues, such as declining living standards, high divorce and crime rates, alcoholism, and corruption. At the same

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time, it exposes the darker aspects of the Russian national character, reflecting real-life societal challenges. Below are several examples:

1. A husband visits a lawyer.
— I want to divorce my wife.
— What happened?
— She goes to restaurants and bars every day.
— Does she drink a lot?
— No, she's looking for me.

Alcohol consumption is deeply embedded in Russian culture, and public intoxication is a common sight. Alcohol plays a crucial role in Russian social life but is also a major cause of family conflicts and high divorce rates. In the joke, the husband wants a divorce not because his wife drinks but because she prevents him from drinking. This highlights weak concepts of marital responsibility. Without an understanding of Russia's social context—especially the cultural significance of alcohol—one might struggle to grasp the humor and the societal reality reflected in this joke.

2. A man and his mother-in-law sit in a room.
The mother-in-law sighs, "Life flies by so quickly: it seems like I was just born, and now it's almost time to die..."
The son-in-law replies, "It's time, it's time..."

Conflicts between sons-in-law and mothers-in-law are one of the most common sources of tension in Russian families. In this joke, the mother-in-law philosophizes about how life has passed quickly, implying she may not have much time left. The son-in-law bluntly agrees, showing his impatience and secret hope for her passing. This humor reflects the stereotypical strained relationship between a man and his wife's mother.

3. A patient calls his doctor to make an appointment.
— Sorry, we can see you in two weeks.
— But by then, I might be dead!
— No problem. If your wife notifies us, we'll cancel the appointment.

This joke highlights issues within Russia's healthcare system. While Russia offers free medical care, it is often criticized for inefficiencies, long waiting times, and bureaucratic indifference. The joke humorously exaggerates the problem—implying that patients might not survive long enough to receive medical attention. The receptionist's unemotional response satirizes the lack of compassion in the system. These examples illustrate different flaws and social habits in Russian daily

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life. On one hand, they reflect the strong sense of humor among Russian people. On the other hand, they demonstrate the Russian tendency to face life's difficulties with irony and acceptance, using humor as a coping mechanism.

Functions of Humorous Discourse. Russians love humor, and humorous discourse plays a significant role in their social and daily interactions. As an essential communication tool, Russian humor not only serves the general communicative functions of language but also possesses unique functions that ordinary language does not. One of the primary functions of humor is to regulate social interactions by softening the mood. Humor reduces the formality and seriousness of a conversation, making the message easier to accept while preventing conflicts and awkwardness.

For example:

A student exits the examination room. His friends ask:

- Well, how did it go? Did you pass?
- I think so...
- What did the professor ask?
- Who knows? He asked in English!

In this joke, the student is aware that he likely performed poorly on the exam. Instead of admitting it directly, he shifts the focus to the professor's use of English, implying that the failure wasn't his fault.

The underlying joke suggests that if the professor had spoken Russian, the student might have passed. This witty response helps the student save face and avoid embarrassment in front of his peers.

This example illustrates how humor can tactfully navigate uncomfortable situations, allowing people to maintain their dignity while deflecting attention from personal shortcomings.

The Emotional Evaluative Function. In everyday communication, people use most words with emotional and subjective evaluation. Humorous discourse is no exception. When people use humor, their subjective feelings are already embedded in humorous texts. Usually, people want to express their dissatisfaction, contempt, mockery, and other emotional evaluations through humor. This is precisely the goal achieved by the speaker through the form of humor.

For example:

- Can your wife cook?
- She can cook, but I just can't eat what she makes.

In this humorous discourse, the husband indirectly evaluates his wife. At first glance, he does not make any negative remarks about her cooking. However, through

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the phrase “but I just can’t eat what she makes,” he clearly expresses his dissatisfaction. Such forms of expression not only enhance the humor but also explicitly convey an evaluative attitude.

The pursuit of joy is a human instinct, especially after experiencing intense pressure, as it can bring lightness and happiness to a person. In this regard, humor fulfills people’s needs. Since laughter is an important manifestation of humor, when people see or hear something humorous, they smile or even laugh out loud. As a result, humor has the effect of calming emotions, releasing pressure, and bringing joy to both body and soul. As a unique national phenomenon of language and culture, Russian humor is an important part of the worldview in linguistic and cultural studies. This article primarily explains humor from the perspectives of its definition, differences from similar concepts, cultural connotations, and its functions in Russian politics and everyday life.

Conclusion. Through analysis, Russian humor is shown to be closely connected with Russian national culture and language. It is difficult to fundamentally understand Russian humor if we separate it from its cultural background. Therefore, when learning the Russian language, we must also pay attention to the combination of language, society, and culture to deepen our understanding of the Russian people.

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